

High-resolution spectroscopy of the star RR Lyrae at high cadence

Zoey Bergstrom

Advisor: Katrien Kolenberg

Harvard University - Cambridge, MA 02138

November 27, 2013

Abstract

This research presents a spectroscopic and photometric analysis of atmospheric dynamics in the variable star RR Lyrae. Pulsating RR Lyrae type stars play an important role in astrophysics as standard candles and as witnesses of galactic evolution. Though they have been studied for over a century, we still do not completely understand several aspects of their pulsations.

The prototype and brightest star of the class, RR Lyrae itself, is probably one of the best-studied stars of its class. Recently, it has been observed by NASA's planet-hunting Kepler mission with a one-minute cadence, resulting in the most precise dataset of an RR Lyrae star in existence. We obtained simultaneous spectroscopy to the Kepler data with a similar cadence (one-minute integrations) using the high-resolution spectrograph attached to the 2.7-m telescope at McDonald observatory. The combination of the spectroscopic and photometric data allows for an unprecedentedly detailed study of the star's atmospheric dynamics, casting light upon some poorly understood aspects of its pulsation.

We investigated how the changes in the star's light curve correlate to properties of its spectrum such as changes in the radial velocity curve derived from different (hydrogen and metal) lines, line broadening and amplitudes. This works towards the constraint of atmospheric parameters such as the macroturbulent velocity of the stellar atmosphere.

1 Introduction

1.1 Kepler Mission and RR Lyrae

The Kepler mission set out in March 2009 to search for extra-solar planets and to improve our knowledge of planetary system structure and abundance by recording planetary transits across bright stellar surfaces. Due to the extended nature of this 3.5 years long mission, and the extremely high precision of its extraterrestrial observations, Kepler has also been a valuable source of data on variable stars (2). Most of these variable star studies occur through the Kepler Asteroseismic Science Consortium (KASC), which employs 1,700 targets per quarter to study the interior of variable stars in the Kepler field (6). These data are often supplemented with ground-based observations.

Our research pertains specifically to RR Lyrae, the prototype RR Lyrae star and the brightest one in the Kepler field. RR Lyrae pulsations are similar to those of Cepheid variables, which is why they are often used as standard candles, but RR Lyrae stars are older and metal poor with relatively low mass (spectral class A or F) (3). RR Lyrae stars have evolved out of the main sequence and now burn He in their cores, which makes their presence an important indicator of galactic evolution. Their typical pulsation periods range from approximately 0.2 days to 1 day, and there are to date about 50 RR Lyrae stars identified in the Kepler field (2). RR Lyrae in particular has a pulsation period of 13hr 36min and an asymmetric heliocentric velocity curve (4). Its intensity varies by about 1 magnitude over the course of its pulsation cycle (see Figure 1).

1.2 Blazhko Effect and Van Hoof Effect

By nature of their pulsation, RR Lyrae stars show light curve variations at each phase of the pulsation period, but many also show longer term modulations in their light curves on the scale of tens to hundreds of days. This long-term periodicity is known as the Blazhko Effect, and it remains a poorly understood phenomenon partly because of the quantity of data needed to properly study it over the course of its period. Figure 2 shows the change in amplitude of RR Lyrae's light curve over a series of pulsation periods, demonstrating the Blazhko Effect. This effect is likely caused by an amalgamation of other effects within the star, and thus must be studied through the combination of more specific hypotheses.

Figure 1: Light curve of RR Lyrae in short cadence (1 minute integration time) over its entire pulsation period of approximately 13.5 hours. Magnitude changes by about 1 magnitude between minimum and maximum intensity.

One such effect involves the atmospheric pulsation dynamics of the star, especially as analyzed through the motions of discrete layers of the photosphere in comparison to the star's overall pulsation. Pulsation models of RR Lyrae stars require a multi-layer photosphere to explain the variable light curves. It has been shown that a phase lag exists between the shifts of the Balmer series and metal lines, which are excited in different depths of the photosphere. This effect, known as the Van Hoof effect, is believed to be a manifestation of sound wave propagation in the stellar atmosphere (4). In recent studies (Mathias Gillet 1993, Mathias et al. 1994) some phase lag has been detected between different metal lines as well. We study this

metal-metal relationship in more detail in our paper.

1.3 The κ -Mechanism

Before we investigate the motions of these photosphere layers, it is important to understand why they occur. The mechanism responsible for the pulsation of RR Lyrae stars is known as the κ -Mechanism. In partially ionized gas, an increase in temperature can lead to increased ionization. With more free electrons, the opacity of the gas increases with temperature, making the atmosphere subject to pulsations. An atmospheric layer contracting inwards into the star will experience an increase in temperature, and consequently an increase in opacity, which will make it difficult for radiation to move from the inside of the star outwards. This radiation instead forces the layer upwards towards cooler temperatures whereupon it becomes less opaque, allows radiation to escape, and falls back in towards high temperature (1). This partial ionization must also occur at a critical depth within the star to sustain a stable pulsation. In RR Lyrae, this mechanism occurs for the layers of partially ionized H and He inside the star. In addition, the Van Hoof Effect can cause the elemental lines (formed an unequal depths) to move out of phase with one another. We investigate this in our study, and provide additional quantitative analysis of the phenomenon.

2 Data and Observations

2.1 Spectroscopy

In our research, we have supplemented the Kepler photometry of RR Lyrae with ground-based spectroscopic data from the Robert G. Tull Coude Spectrograph on the 2.7-m telescope at McDonald observatory to study the behavior of specific elements in its atmosphere. This telescope has a cross-dispersed echelle spectrograph which has a resolving power of $R \approx 60,000$. Our data span three nights: August 24th, 26th, and 30th, 2010 (hereafter nights 1, 3, and 6). The spectroscopic data is of a high cadence with 1 minute integration times, which is very short in order to minimize smearing of the spectral features. Bias and flat-field frames were obtained at the beginning of each night and the data were reduced using the Image Reduction and Analysis Facility (IRAF) (2).

Wavelength (Å)	Element	Night 1 Range (Å)	Night 3 Range (Å)	Night 6 Range (Å)
5167.327	Mg I	5165.8-5167.4	5165-5166.6	5165-5167
5172.698	Mg I	5171.1-5172.7	5170.4-5171.9	5170.9-5172.2
5183.619	Mg I	5181.9-5183.5	5181.2-5182.8	5181.8-5183.1
4340.5	H γ	4337.5-4341.5	4334.0-4341.5	4334.0-4342.0
4101.7	H δ	4097.0-4105.0	4090.0-4103.0	4092.0-4106.0
5233.94	Fe I	5231.3-5233	5230.7-5232.2	5231.2-5232.4
5169.033	Fe II	5167.4-5169.0	5166.7-5168.2	5167.2-5168.6
5185.913	Ti II	5184.4-5186.0	5183.7-5185.1	5184.2-5185.3
5188.68	Ti II	5187.2-5188.5	5186.4-5188.0	5186.8-5188.2

Table 1: Laboratory wavelengths of the selected Balmer and metallic lines in our study. The range for each night is the range of Doppler shift including the entire line width - from continuum to continuum. Table formatted by Sam Horan.

Our data range from 3700-11050Å, with several gaps occurring over short wavelength intervals beginning after 5800Å. Within this range we initially chose two Balmer lines (H- γ and H- δ) and seven metallic lines for detailed inspection and Doppler analysis (see Table 1). These lines were chosen because they were completely unblended and had significant intensity. By associating these lines with their excitation temperatures and consequently with specific depths in the stellar atmosphere, we could model the complexity of the star’s atmospheric dynamics in great detail - a project we may pursue in future studies. In this Doppler analysis, we have kept in mind that RR Lyrae is traveling towards us at 74 km/s, causing an overall blueshift in our spectra. Additionally, due to the changes in the light curve over time, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) varies as a function of the star’s intensity.

The normalization of these data was a non-trivial task. In the raw data we received, each of the 230 spectra was subdivided into 62 shorter-range spectra coming from each of the echelle orders. The data from each order needed to have its blaze shape individually fit with a low order polynomial. The fit must include the entire continuum without fitting the spectral features, particularly wide features such as the Balmer series (2). We completed this normalization using a SPLINE3 fitting via IRAF’s continuum package. We then divided the raw spectra by the normalized spectra to get the curve of the fit. Using the task SCOMBINE we combined the raw spectra into one long spectrum, and also combined together the curve fits. The combined raw spectra were then divided by the combined curve fits to get the final

normalized spectrum at each integration time. This method is more effective than simply using a SPLINE3 fit for each spectrum and combining the results because some of the wavelength ranges of adjacent gratings overlapped, which this more extensive process takes into account. Unfortunately, the spectra included several flaws which could not be removed through normalization, one of which fell on the range of the H- β line. Furthermore, the H- α line at 6563Å was also within the range of our data but fell within one of the wavelength gaps.

We then imported ASCII files for each set of spectroscopic data into FAMIAS (Frequency Analysis and Mode Identification for Asteroseismology) (5). For each of the selected absorption lines, we extracted the relevant dispersion range (see Table 1) and converted the horizontal wavelength axis into radial velocity in km/s based on the laboratory wavelength zeropoints for each element. The spectra were then weighted by their signal-to-noise and line extracted before producing moment 1 (radial velocity) graphs. The computation of moment n (ν^n) taking into account the velocity of the star with respect to the sun is as follows:

$$\nu_{I(t)}^n = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \nu^n I(\nu, t) d\nu}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I(\nu, t) d\nu} \quad (1)$$

where I(t) is the intensity as a function of time.

In our SNR analysis in FAMIAS, the SNR of each spectrum gets saved as a weight value where $W = SNR^2$ and the complete set of weight values is normalized such that the average value is one. In our radial velocity plots, we removed points that were clearly poor signal-to-noise outliers. Such outliers caused issue in FAMIAS during line extraction and therefore were unreliable.

It is also interesting to note that one of our chosen lines, Ti II (5185.913), makes a delayed appearance in the night 3 data. There is no significant trace of it until the 10th spectrum at Heliocentric Julian Date 2455434.70351865, which we expect to be a temperature effect.

2.2 Photometry

We obtained photometric data corresponding to the times of both the night 1 and night 6 spectroscopic observations. The photometry for these nights shows that each set was taken during a different part of RR Lyrae’s pulsation. By correlating the Heliocentric Julian Date of the photometric and spectro-

scopic data, we can map changes in the spectra during different phases of the overall pulsation. Figure 3 shows when in the pulsation cycle each set of data was taken.

There are many important features to note about the light curves shown in Figure 3. First of all, it should be noted that the phase of minimum radius occurs in the middle of the rising branch of the light curve, rather than at peak intensity as one might expect. This is likely due to a combination of effects. One theory is that, during the phase of minimum radius, radiation is trapped in the deeper layers and the star therefore does not reach maximum light until this radiation can travel through to the photosphere, which forces the process out of phase. Because the layers of the photosphere do not move exactly in phase with each other, the peak of maximum intensity actually corresponds to the phase of maximum temperature. Similarly, the phase of maximum radius occurs in the approximate middle of the falling branch of the light curve at the point of minimum temperature, as shown in Figure 3 (2). The phase of maximum radius (quiescent phase) is believed to have the best-behaved atmospheric dynamics for modelling.

It is also significant to note that there are two shock waves that propagate through the star during pulsation. If phase 0.0 corresponds to maximum intensity, the main shock wave occurs around $\phi = 0.9$, with the secondary shock wave around $\phi = 0.7$. These shock waves can cause line broadening, doubling, and/or disappearance at the part of the phase where they occur (2)

The spectroscopy of night 6 covers the phase of minimum radius, and that of night 1 covers the phase of maximum radius. This is interesting because, since these points have already been established as the maximum and minimum for radial velocity of the star as a whole, we should be able to see a phase lag of the pulsation velocity in the atmosphere, as depicted by the hydrogen and metallic line shifts.

3 Analysis

To analyze the phase lag between the different combinations of lines, we plotted velocity-velocity graphs for different combinations of elements in the stellar spectrum. If the radial velocities of the two lines being plotted are consistently identical and therefore moving together, the graph would pro-

duce a straight line with slope = 1. However, if the motion of the two lines is not precisely in phase, the graph will be shifted. In fact, if one has spectroscopic data to cover the entire pulsation period the graph becomes a loop. If the width of the loop is larger than the velocity uncertainty, this difference becomes significant.

One problem we encountered was that the Balmer series lines each had several smaller lines blended into them, which affected our radial velocity calculations. We chose to integrate over the entire line width and find the center of the weight of the line to determine the redshift/blueshift, rather than using the point of minimum intensity, which means any blended spectral features significantly alter the calculation. For this reason, we chose to focus more on entirely unblended metal lines and their relationships to each other over the three nights. In future research, we will study the Balmer series lines through alternative methods which are less dependent on the blend and linewidth to calculate the radial velocity.

In order to get a sense of which lines may be moving independently from one another, we first plotted the radial velocity of each line as a function of time for each night. A graph for night 1 is shown in Figure 4. From these graphs, it became apparent that the Ti II (5188.68Å) line and the Mg I (5167.327Å) line do not always move with the same velocity as the other metals. These graphs also demonstrated the large scatter of H- γ and H- δ compared to the metal lines, which is why we chose to omit them from our analysis.

From this information, we selected lines with interesting behavior to plot in velocity-velocity graphs to investigate possible phase lags. The graphs we produced include Fe II (5169.033Å) vs. Mg I (5167.327Å), Mg I (5167.327Å) vs. Ti II (5188.68Å), and Mg II (5172.698Å) vs. Ti II (5188.68Å), the first of which is shown in Figure 5.

3.1 Error Analysis

The error calculations for this study are quite complex. Because we used integration to find the center of weight for each line and determine its radial velocity, the statistical error involves the line width and consequently the range over which we integrated. To perform this error calculation, we changed the bounds of integration for each line by ± 5 km/s and determined the standard deviation for the resulting change in radial velocity measurement. The results of this are shown in Table 2, and all fell within the range 0.07 km/s

Wavelength (Å)	Element	$\sigma - \text{Night1}$	$\sigma - \text{Night3}$	$\sigma - \text{Night6}$
5167.327	Mg I	0.238807	0.289256	0.085232
5172.698	Mg I	0.331373	0.149624	0.092678
5183.619	Mg I	0.112589	0.072711	0.081814
5169.033	Fe II	0.192437	0.265085	0.304755
5185.913	Ti II	0.311610	0.170166	0.082219
5188.68	Ti II	0.071233	0.213495	0.375501

Table 2: Table of standard deviation values for each metal line on each night in units of km/s.

$\leq \sigma \leq 0.38$ km/s. This is a surprisingly good statistical error considering these are very short cadence spectra with low signal-to-noise.

Further error analysis can be performed in the future by factoring in the SNR and telescope resolution, uncertainties produced by the normalization, and atomic physics uncertainties. These calculations will be examined in detail in our ongoing research.

4 Conclusions and Future Outlook

The aim of the study presented in this paper was to test the extent of the Van Hoof Effect in the star RR Lyrae through analysis of the atmospheric dynamics as seen in the motions of metal lines in its spectrum. Herein we have established that various metal lines do in fact move out of phase with one another, including magnesium, titanium, and iron. We also saw that calculating the first moment works well to analyze completely unblended lines such as these, but for wider lines such as the Balmer series this analysis produces a high scatter that renders the lines unusable. Alternative methods could include selecting the point of minimum intensity as the line’s radial velocity, or using a Gaussian fit model. We opted against these methods because of the asymmetrical nature of our spectral features. For lines without spherical symmetry it is most effective to get an accurate line weight by calculating moment 1.

This study is particularly exciting because never before have we been able to compare the photometry of RR Lyrae’s light curve to simultaneous spectra of such short cadence. This small integration time prevented smearing of

the spectral features, allowing a more accurate analysis of the lines than ever before. By fitting low order polynomials to the blaze of each echelle grating, we normalized the data to high precision. We were then able to analyze the progression of the lines' radial velocities in FAMIAS and plot them against each other to map their relationships over the course of the star's pulsation.

In the future, we hope to quantify the radial velocity shift between lines in greater detail with the addition of error bars. There are also many opportunities for further data analysis. It is still not well-understood why the night 6 data behaves as it does, with positive and increasing radial velocities over time when we were expecting to find blueshift at that phase. Additionally, the shift between Fe I (5233.94\AA) and the other lines was much greater than anticipated (approximately 35km/s faster than the other metals at any given point). Our first thought on this matter was a misidentification of the Fe I line, but other nearby lines produce an even more drastic divergence. We hope to study this unusual occurrence more in the near future.

References

- [1] de Boer, K.S. et al. 2008, Stars and Stellar Evolution, EDP Sciences
- [2] Kolenberg, K. et al. 2010, The Astrophysical Journal Letters, 713, 198-203
- [3] Layden A.C. et al. 1996, The Astrophysical Journal, 112, 2110-2131
- [4] Mathias, P. et al. 1994, Astronomy and Astrophysics, 298, 843-848
- [5] Zima, W. 2008, Communications in Asteroseismology 155
- [6] <http://kepler.nasa.gov/>

Figure 2: Intensity over time plotted for RR Lyrae through several pulsation periods, demonstrating the long term periodicity of the Blazhko Effect. (Figure by KK)

Figure 3: Photometry of nights 1 and 6. Each dot corresponds to one 1 minute integration time on the spectrograph. Night 1: Spectroscopic data begins during expansion phase of the star’s overall pulsation, covers maximum radius, and ends during contraction. Night 6: Spectroscopic data begins during contraction phase of star’s overall pulsation, covers minimum radius, and ends during expansion. The points of maximum and minimum radius are labelled. (Figures by KK)

Figure 4: Six of the nine observed lines plotted against time during night 1, using -74km/s (the overall velocity of RR Lyrae in the Sun's reference frame) as the radial velocity zeropoint. Note that the Mg I (5167.327Å) line and the Ti (5188.68Å) line are slightly shifted from the other metals. Balmer series lines omitted due to large scatter, and Fe I (5233.94Å) line omitted due to unusual behavior. This Fe I line will be studied in our continuing research.

Figure 5: Velocity-velocity plot of Fe II (5169.033\AA) vs. Mg I (5167.327\AA). The straight line indicates where the data should have fallen if the two elements were moving entirely in phase with each other, which clearly they are not. The other two velocity-velocity graphs produced a similar result, with slightly different shifts.